

Conjugate heat transfer in MHD flow due to a linearly stretching sheet

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Abstract

Conjugate study of heat transfer for a stretching sheet, whose surface is exposed to a cooling fluid, is performed through curve fitting. The analysis of the problem leads to a set of linear problems, which are solved recursively. The physical processes of heat diffusion and viscous dissipation in both media, as well as Joule heating and magnetic induction in the MHD fluid flow are retained. Examples involving cases of prescribed surface temperature, prescribed surface flux, and a conductive sheet are considered. Useful information on the surface temperature and/or the surface heat flux are obtained.

1. Introduction

Two interrelated problems captured the interest of researchers for decades; Sakiadis flow (SF) due to uniform motion of a sheet [1] and Crane's flow (CF) due to stretching of a sheet [2]. Their application in extrusion processes demands the study of the associated thermal problems, since the quality of the end product depends on the involved heat transfer processes. Several factors and related parameters were put under scrutiny; e.g. farfield flow (speed ratio), surface feed (suction rate), velocity and thermal slip, non-Newtonian fluids, hydro-magnetic effects (Hartmann number, magnetic Reynolds number), chemical reaction, viscous dissipation, heat generation, radiation. For references, mostly related to CF of current concern, see [3-24] and the references therein.

The mathematical modeling of the thermal problems usually concentrates on the fluid flow; imposing surface conditions of specified temperature or heat flux of different forms [4,7,11,17]. The rare alternative is the conjugate heat analysis involving both the fluid and the sheet [5,6,8,10,13,16], the simplest form of which is to apply a "convective" condition [19,22]. Kuiken [5] used a global energy balance in SF, which was also adopted by Afzal and Varshney [10] in CF (with power-law stretching). Vleggaar [8] in CF used an energy equation for the sheet involving dissipation and diffusion of heat along the sheet. Char et al. [13] added convection and neglected dissipation. In SF, Sparrow and Abraham [18] involved diffusion along the sheet. Refs. [5,10,8,13,18], dealing with a symmetrically double-wetted sheet, allowed only for variation in temperature along the sheet. In a short penetration extent, Chida and Katto [6] in SF allowed for temperature variation across the sheet, involving lateral conduction, and Mendez and Trevino [16] added diffusion along the sheet.

In search for solutions to the conjugate problems, mostly numerical methods were adopted. Kuiken [5] and Afzal and Varshney [10] obtained series solutions. Sparrow and Abraham [18] curve-fitted the temperature variation along the sheet by a quadratic expression whose coefficients were obtained iteratively.

We formulate a conjugate thermal problem for a linearly-stretching sheet and the associated MHD flow. A linear distribution of temperature across the sheet is assumed; the sheet being thin with one wet and one dry sides. The traditionally ignored physical processes of heat diffusion and viscous dissipation in both media, as well as Joule heating and magnetic induction in the fluid are retained. Flow field equations (Navier-stokes', Maxwell's and Ohm's) with available exact solutions [24] are adopted. Other effects such as surface feed, velocity slip, thermal slip with shear work [23], radiation and heat generation are not but can be included.

A curve fitting expression for the temperature is proposed. Thus the thermal problem is reduced to a set of linear problems, which are solved recursively.

2. Flow description

An electrically conducting, incompressible, Newtonian fluid is driven by a non-conducting non-porous sheet, which is stretching linearly in the x -direction with rate ω . In the farfield, the fluid is essentially quiescent under pressure $p = p_\infty$ and temperature $T = T_\infty$, and is permeated by a stationary magnetic field of uniform strength B in the transverse y -direction. The velocity components in the (x,y) directions are (u,v) and the corresponding induced magnetic field components are (r,s) . Constants are the fluid density ρ_f , kinematic viscosity ϑ_f , electric conductivity σ_f , magnetic permeability μ_f , specific heat c_f , and thermal conductivity k_f and the sheet density ρ_s , kinematic viscosity ϑ_s , specific heat c_s , and thermal conductivity k_s . The main nondimensional flow parameters, to be involved below, are the Prandtl number $P_r = \rho_f \vartheta_f c_f / k_f$, the magnetic Prandtl number $P_m = \sigma_f \mu_f \vartheta_f$, and the magnetic interaction number $\beta = \sigma_f B^2 / \rho_f \omega$.

3. Analysis of the MHD flow problem

The MHD flow problem is governed by the following field equations and boundary conditions [23].

$$u_x + v_y = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$\rho_f (uu_x + vv_y) + p_x = \rho_f \vartheta_f (u_{xx} + v_{yy}) + \sigma_f [(B + s)rv - (B + s)^2 u] \quad (1b)$$

$$\rho_f (uv_x + vv_y) + p_y = \rho_f \vartheta_f (v_{xx} + v_{yy}) + \sigma_f [(B + s)ru - r^2 v] \quad (1c)$$

$$s_x - r_y = \sigma_f \mu_f [(B + s)u - rv] \quad (1d)$$

$$r_x + s_y = 0 \quad (1e)$$

$$u = \omega x, v = 0 \text{ at } y = 0 \quad (1f)$$

$$u \sim 0, p \sim p_\infty, r \sim 0, s \sim 0 \text{ as } y \sim \infty \quad (1g)$$

The substitutions [24]

$$x = \chi \sqrt{\vartheta_f / \omega}, y = \zeta \sqrt{\vartheta_f / \omega} \gamma \quad (2a,b)$$

$$u = \sqrt{\vartheta_f \omega} \chi e^{-\zeta}, v = -\sqrt{\vartheta_f \omega} (1 - e^{-\zeta}) / \gamma, r = B P_m \chi \lambda \gamma e^{-\zeta}, s = B P_m \lambda e^{-\zeta} \quad (2c,d,e,f)$$

$$p = p_\infty - \rho_f \vartheta_f \omega \left[(\gamma^2 - 1) e^{-\zeta} + \frac{1}{2} e^{-2\zeta} + \frac{1}{2} \beta P_m \chi^2 \lambda^2 \gamma^4 e^{-2\zeta} \right] / \gamma^2 \quad (2g)$$

render the MHD flow problem identically satisfied, provided that γ and λ are given by

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\left[(\beta + 1 + P_m) + \sqrt{(\beta + 1 + P_m)^2 - 4P_m} \right] / 2} \quad (3a)$$

$$\lambda = 2 / \left[(\beta + 1 - P_m) + \sqrt{(\beta + 1 + P_m)^2 - 4P_m} \right] \quad (3b)$$

4. Analysis of the thermal problem

The energy equation for the fluid, retaining viscous dissipation and Joule heating, writes [23]

$$\rho_f c_f (uT_x + vT_y) = k_f (T_{xx} + T_{yy}) + \rho_f \vartheta_f [2(u_x^2 + v_y^2) + (u_y + v_x)^2] + \sigma_f [(B + s)u - rv]^2 \quad (4a)$$

with the farfield condition

$$T \sim T_\infty \text{ as } y \sim \infty \quad (4b)$$

Fig. 1: Heat transfer for a differential element of the sheet

Within the sheet, being of small thickness h , we adopt a linear y -wise distribution of temperature. Denote the temperature of the wet side (exposed to the fluid) of the sheet by $T_w(x)$, that of the other (dry) side by $T_d(x)$, and their mean value by $T_m(x)$. The energy equation for the electrically non-conducting, stretching sheet is similar to Eq. (4a), with the terms involving the y -wise velocity component and the Joule heating term dropped. It writes (See also Fig. 1.),

$$\rho_s c_s \omega \frac{dx T_m}{dx} = k_s \frac{\partial^2 T_m}{\partial x^2} + \frac{1}{h} \left[k_f \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \Big|_w - k_s \frac{T_w - T_d}{h} \right] + 2\rho_s \vartheta_s \omega^2 \quad (4c)$$

The left hand side represents x -wise heat convection, while the terms on the right hand side represent x -wise heat diffusion, y -wise heat diffusion, and viscous dissipation, respectively. [For a symmetrically double-wetted sheet, we set $T_d = T_w$ in (4c) and double k_f .]

Now, given

$$T_d = T_\infty + Q_d(x) \quad (5)$$

Eq. (4c) gives the boundary condition for T at $y = 0$. If viscous dissipation and the x -wise convection and diffusion are neglected, we end up with the conductive sheet condition (termed “convective” condition in [19,22])

$$k_f \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = k_s \frac{T - T_d}{h} \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (6a)$$

If, further, $k_f/k_s \approx 0$ or $h \approx 0$, we end up with the prescribed surface temperature condition

$$T = T_d = T_\infty + Q_w(x) \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (6b)$$

where, Q_d has been replaced by Q_w , for convenience.

If, on the other hand, $k_s/k_f \approx 0$, we end up with the adiabatic wall condition

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (6c)$$

This is a special case of the condition of prescribed heat flux to the sheet $q_w(x)$,

$$k_f \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = -q_w(x) \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (6d)$$

which is rather impractical to impose, but can be looked at as a design condition.

Following Sparrow and Abraham [18], we propose a polynomial expression for T ,

$$T = T_\infty + \frac{\vartheta_f \omega}{c_f} \sum_{n=0}^N \theta_n(\zeta) \chi^n \quad (7)$$

This is not an expansion for small x but, rather, a curve-fit. In the same spirit, to handle the functions Q_d , Q_w and q_w which may be arbitrary, we curve-fit them by polynomials of degree N ,

$$Q_d = \frac{\vartheta_f \omega}{c_f} \sum_{n=0}^N a_n \chi^n \quad (8a)$$

$$Q_w = \frac{\vartheta_f \omega}{c_f} \sum_{n=0}^N b_n \chi^n \quad (8b)$$

$$q_w = k_f \frac{\gamma}{\sqrt{\vartheta_f/\omega}} \frac{\vartheta_f \omega}{c_f} \sum_{n=0}^N c_n \chi^n \quad (8b)$$

Substituting the expressions (2c,d,e,f) for u , v , r and s and (7) for T in the energy equation (4a) and equating coefficients of the same powers of χ on both sides lead to a set of equations for the temperature constituents θ_n , $n = N \rightarrow 0$, which can be combined as

$$\theta_n'' + \delta(1 - e^{-\zeta})\theta_n' - n\delta e^{-\zeta}\theta_n = A_n\theta_{n+2} + B_n e^{-2\zeta} + C_n e^{-2\zeta} \quad (9a)$$

where a prime denotes differentiation with respect to ζ , $\delta = P_r/\gamma^2$, and

$$A_N = 0, \quad A_{N-1} = 0, \quad A_n = -[(n+2)(n+1)/\gamma^2], \quad n = N-2 \rightarrow 0$$

$$B_2 = -P_r, \quad B_0 = -4\delta, \quad B_{n \neq 2,0} = 0, \quad n = N \rightarrow 0$$

$$C_2 = -\beta P_m \lambda^2 \gamma^2, \quad C_{n \neq 2} = 0, \quad n = N \rightarrow 0$$

In the right hand side of (9a), the term involving A_n corresponds to streamwise diffusion, that involving B_n corresponds to viscous dissipation, and the one involving C_n corresponds to Joule heating.

Likewise, substituting (7) in the boundary conditions (4b,c) and using (8a), for instance, lead for $n = N \rightarrow 0$ to

$$\theta_n(\infty) = 0 \quad (9b)$$

$$\theta'_n(0) = \left[\frac{\bar{k}}{\gamma^2 \bar{h}} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho} \bar{c} \bar{h} P_r n \right] \theta_n(0) - j_1 \frac{1}{2} \bar{h} \bar{k} (n+2)(n+1) \theta_{n+2}(0) - \frac{\bar{k}}{\gamma^2 \bar{h}} a_n - j_2 2 \bar{\rho} \bar{\vartheta} \bar{h} P_r \quad (9c)$$

where

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f}, \quad \bar{\vartheta} = \frac{\vartheta_s}{\vartheta_f}, \quad \bar{c} = \frac{c_s}{c_f}, \quad \bar{k} = \frac{k_s}{k_f}, \quad \bar{h} = \frac{h}{\gamma \sqrt{\vartheta_f / \omega}}$$

and

$$j_1 = \begin{cases} 0 & n = N \rightarrow N-1 \\ 1 & n = N-2 \rightarrow 0 \end{cases}, \quad j_2 = \begin{cases} 0 & n \neq 0 \\ 1 & n = 0 \end{cases}$$

In particular, the degenerate condition (6a) becomes

$$\theta'_n(0) = \kappa [\theta_n(0) - a_n], \quad \kappa = \frac{\bar{k}}{\gamma^2 \bar{h}} \quad (10a)$$

Similarly, the degenerate conditions (6b,c,d) give

$$\theta_n(0) = b_n \quad (10b)$$

$$\theta'_n(0) = 0 \quad (10c)$$

$$\theta'_n(0) = -c_n \quad (10d)$$

Note that, in contrast to the iterative procedure of Sparrow and Abraham [18], the current procedure is recursive.

5. Numerical treatment and sample results

The problem described by Eqs. (9a,b,c) has an infinite domain that can be transformed into a finite domain by the transformation

$$z = e^{-\zeta} \quad (14)$$

With a prime denoting differentiation with respect to z , the problem becomes

$$z^2 \theta''_n + [(1-\delta)z + \delta z^2] \theta'_n - n \delta z \theta_n = A_n \theta_{n+2} + B_n z^2 + C_n z^2 \quad (15a)$$

$$\theta_n(0) = 0 \quad (15b)$$

$$\theta'_n(1) + \left[\kappa + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho} \bar{c} \bar{h} P_r n \right] \theta_n(1) = j_1 \frac{1}{2} \bar{h} \bar{k} (n+2)(n+1) \theta_{n+2}(1) + \kappa a_n + j_2 2 \bar{\rho} \bar{\vartheta} \bar{h} P_r \quad (15c)$$

It is a linear problem with split boundary conditions, which can be solved efficiently by the exponential box scheme [25].

a. Constant $Q_d = 1$

b. Constant $Q_d = 1$

c. Constant $Q_w = 1$

d. Constant $Q_w = 1$

e. Constant $q_w = 1$

f. Constant $q_w = 1$ and $q_w = 0$

g. Constant $q_w = 0$

Fig. 2: Thermal Profiles.

Table 1: Heat flux constituents, $\theta'_n(z = 1)$, $n = 0 \rightarrow N$, for increasing values of N .

$n \vdots N$	2	4	6	8	10
10					0.0000022318
9					-0.0000211971
8				0.0001801427	0.0001786248
7				-0.0013509839	-0.0013380963
6			0.0087827533	0.0086862733	0.0086858159
5			-0.0483331611	-0.0477079125	-0.0477045290
4		0.2178174922	0.2143959445	0.2143744151	0.2143741905
3		-0.7650340322	-0.7497759833	-0.7496616090	-0.7496602378
2	0.3325172489	0.2800662745	0.2795823501	0.2795755582	0.2795754611
1	-2.9848002738	-2.8591280923	-2.8576343772	-2.8576092660	-2.8576088526
0	-6.9120159431	-6.9146896509	-6.9147449764	-6.9147460406	-6.9147460591
$\theta'_w _{\chi=1}$	-9.5642989680	-10.0409680088	-10.0677274501	-10.0682594227	-10.0682626478

Table 2a: Sample results of curve-fitting parabola, given $Q_d = \exp(-\chi)$

χ	$\theta(\chi)$	$\theta'(\chi)$	$\theta(\chi)$	$\theta'(\chi)$
0.0	0.0000000000	0.0033324738	0.0000000000	0.0033324738
0.1	0.0436682649	0.9363422882	0.0436682550	0.9363417068
0.2	0.2076018464	2.4770063917	0.2076013680	2.4769938919
0.3	0.5654745121	4.7795511790	0.5654710083	4.7794980495
0.4	1.1695842412	7.2527264891	1.1695724329	7.2526124449
0.5	1.9903349264	8.9672618608	1.9903089747	8.9670975108
0.6	2.9159332954	9.2884388788	2.9158898792	9.2882613621
0.7	3.7980332429	8.1248308560	3.7979732884	8.1246846333
0.8	4.5025160730	5.8157539357	4.5024446196	5.8156751137
0.9	4.9405499701	2.8865134530	4.9404750403	2.8865259454
1.0	5.0760686204	-0.1600784313	5.0760002578	-0.1599564649
Case	Truncated Exponential Expansion		Curve-Fitting Parabola	

Table 2b: Sample results of curve-fitting parabola, given $Q_w = \exp(-\chi)$

χ	$\theta(\chi)$	$\theta'(\chi)$	$\theta(\chi)$	$\theta'(\chi)$
0.0	0.0000000000	0.0033324738	0.0000000000	0.0033324738
0.1	0.0435564958	0.9295525247	0.0435561458	0.9295326626
0.2	0.2012372982	2.3010667912	0.2012236144	2.3007395595
0.3	0.5113075769	3.8765041618	0.5112289698	3.8755253855
0.4	0.9566268136	4.8591827386	0.9564338888	4.8580446863
0.5	1.4390989976	4.5407727765	1.4388368381	4.5407619818
0.6	1.8151810671	2.7523962274	1.8150265624	2.7547090669
0.7	1.9517477050	-0.1629436666	1.9519658888	-0.1577599645
0.8	1.7645646944	-3.6203024727	1.7654548327	-3.6119708168
0.9	1.2286527097	-7.0547457309	1.2305731855	-7.0421415728
1.0	0.3678794643	-10.0682626478	0.3713983475	-10.0481139296
Case	Truncated Exponential Expansion		Curve-Fitting Parabola	

Table 2c: Sample results of curve-fitting parabola, given $q_w = \exp(-\chi)$

χ	$\theta(\chi)$	$\theta'(\chi)$	$\theta(\chi)$	$\theta'(\chi)$
0.0	0.0000000000	0.0033324738	0.0000000000	0.0033324738
0.1	0.0436834321	0.9372585585	0.0436831353	0.9372410502
0.2	0.2084372590	2.4998184978	0.2084228334	2.4994412804
0.3	0.5723396401	4.8914905988	0.5722337870	4.8898835827
0.4	1.1955541311	7.5340653323	1.1951967062	7.5306061225
0.5	2.0547285605	9.4550571906	2.0539413289	9.4500533779
0.6	3.0384642341	9.9533826863	3.0371438850	9.9479477228
0.7	3.9927093871	8.8869184673	3.9908805073	8.8823958792
0.8	4.7741656721	6.5770358439	4.7719775380	6.5745238488
0.9	5.2845784914	3.5604227128	5.2822713224	3.5606516397
1.0	5.4805437376	0.3678794643	5.4784193017	0.3713983475
Case	Truncated Exponential Expansion		Curve-Fitting Parabola	

For concrete examples, we consider the MHD flow of seawater due to the stretching of a thin polystyrene sheet for which $\beta = 0.1$, $P_m \approx 0$, $P_r = 7.3$ and $\kappa = 0.034$.

For simplicity, we adopt the degenerate conditions

$$\theta'_n(1) = \kappa[a_n - \theta_n(1)] \quad (16a)$$

$$\theta_n(1) = b_n \quad (16b)$$

$$\theta'_n(1) = 0 \quad (16c)$$

$$\theta'_n(1) = c_n \quad (16d)$$

As a first test case, we consider a sheet in a uniform state; i.e., Q_d , Q_w or q_w is constant. Then, only the corresponding leading coefficient a_0 , b_0 or c_0 in Eqs. (7) does not vanish and, regardless of N , only θ_0 and θ_2 are involved. Figures (2a-f) show the profiles of $[\theta_0(z)$ and $\theta'_0(z)]$ and $[\theta_2(z)$ and $\theta'_2(z)]$ when a_0 , b_0 or c_0 is unity. The profiles for $[\theta_0(z)$ and $\theta'_0(z)]$, when the sheet is thermally insulated ($c_0 = 0$), is shown in Fig. (2g) while those for $[\theta_2(z)$ and $\theta'_2(z)]$ are the same as those when $c_0 = 1$.

In the second test case, we first approximate $Q_w = \exp(-\chi)$, $0 \leq \chi \leq 1$, by a truncated exponential expansion, in which $b_n = (-1)^n/n!$ for $n = 0 \rightarrow N$. By gradually increasing N , we hope to arrive at a saturated solution, which would represent the case of $Q_w = \exp(-\chi)$ accurately. This proved to be feasible as Table 1 indicates.

The last line in Table 1 gives the heat flux to the fluid at $\chi = 1$,

$$\theta'_w|_{\chi=1} = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{d\theta_n}{dz} \Big|_{z=1} = - \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{d\theta_n}{d\zeta} \Big|_{\zeta=0} \quad (11)$$

The choices $N = 6, 8$ and 10 exhibit 3 decimal point agreement of the constituents and 5 significant figure agreement of their sums. Thus, the truncated expansion with $N = 10$ is deemed accurate to represent $\exp(-\chi)$, $0 \leq \chi \leq 1$. Similar conclusions are reached when $Q_d = \exp(-\chi)$ or $q_w = \exp(-\chi)$.

The simplest curve that fits $\exp(-\chi)$ at $\chi = n/10$, $n = 0 \rightarrow 10$ is the parabola

$$y(\chi) = 0.9961122964 - 0.9343481545\chi + 0.3096342056\chi^2 \quad (12)$$

The results it produces coincide with those of the truncated exponential expansion with $N = 10$, within plotting accuracy. Sample numeral results are given in Tables 2.

6. Conclusion

The conjugate thermal problem associated with the problem of the MHD flow due to a linearly stretching sheet with induced magnetic field is formulated. In the energy equation of the flow, the traditionally ignored processes of streamwise heat diffusion, viscous dissipation and Joule heating are retained. Moreover, by considering the energy equation of the sheet, a general form for the thermal boundary condition on the flow at the sheet surface is derived and shown to degenerate to simpler conditions in common use.

A curve-fitting polynomial is introduced to approximate the flow temperature. This leads to a set of linear problems, involving ordinary differential equations in the transverse coordinate with split boundary conditions, whose solutions are obtained recursively.

Two examples are treated. The curve-fitting approach proved to be simple and accurate.

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